

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF INTERNAL ANTI-CORRUPTION MEASURES IN THE PREVENTION OF CORRUPTION OFFENSES

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Abstract. The article describes the role and significance of internal anti-corruption measures in the prevention of corruption offenses. In particular, the relevance and importance of taking effective measures in view of the number and volume of corruption offenses, as well as some features of the issues, the lack of clear regulation of internal procedures that need to be identified and measures taken to address them are indicated. The study provides a causal method for analyzing the issue of effective regulation of legal relations, that is, the sufficiency of control measures, compliance with established norms, which are aimed at the effectiveness of anti-corruption measures and ensuring the development of a society without corruption. The system of measures to prevent corruption provided for in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Corruption" is analyzed. Anti-corruption measures is not effective, and sometimes exacerbates the position of state bodies in front of the public. In this regard, the assessment of corruption risks arising from the implementation of the assigned tasks and functions, which must be formed on the basis of internal and external sources, is of particular importance.

Key words: corruption offenses, legal relations, monitoring of possible risks, measures to prevent corruption, anti-corruption programs of government agencies.

Introduction

During the implementation of in-depth reforms in various sectors of the country's life, the issue of establishing and applying effective anti-corruption

measures by state bodies remains relevant. Since the object of corruption offenses are public relations that arise between individuals (legal entities) persons and organizations, represented by public officials.

At the moment, the legislation does not clearly distinguish between them, but does not exclude their presence either. This circumstance begins and ends in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Combating Corruption” (Adolat, 2017), which defines corruption as the illegal use by a person of his official or official position in order to obtain material or non-material benefits in his personal interests or in the interests of other persons, as well as the illegal provision of such benefits.

Theoretical and practical framework

According to M. Weber, power is the ability to carry out one’s own will even in spite of resistance (Weber, 1990). In other words, non-compliance with the established norms of behavior in society by a person who has authority in order to obtain an unlawful advantage for himself or in the interests of third parties. This circumstance indicates that the list of corruption offenses cannot be exhaustive and clearly fixed. But, nevertheless, it is important to indicate which corruption torts should be qualified as criminally punishable acts, administratively punishable violations, and maybe even civil, disciplinary or even ethical offenses.

At the same time, it should also be noted the assessment of international experts of the OECD, whose analysis is based on the study of 13 types of crimes provided for by the Criminal Code (Art. 167, 168, 192-9, 192-10, 192- 11, 205, 206, 211, 212, 213, 214, 243) (OECD, 2019). Which, in turn, argues that today the legislation defines corruption crimes, and not corruption offenses, although the Law “On Combating Corruption” determines that a corruption offense is an act that has signs of corruption, for which the legislation provides for liability. In this regard, the question arises in which actions or events a person, by virtue of his official or official position, violates the established norms in order to obtain material or non-material benefits in his personal interests or in the interests of other persons, as well as

illegally provides such benefits.. The study of this issue has shown that without a clear and transparent regulation of these two elements, which are an integral part of the legal fact and, consequently, the very meaning of the legal relationship, it is not possible to minimize corruption risks or even eliminate¹.

This leads to the paradox of how effectively the legal relationship is regulated: Are there sufficient control measures? Are the established norms observed or are there gaps in them? All this leads to the fact that state bodies and other organizations must take measures that would answer the above questions and, as a result, would serve to establish anti-corruption measures and ensure the development of a society without corruption.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to further improve the system of combating corruption in the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated May 27, 2019 No.DP–5729 (Adolat, 2019), it is determined that the primary task of the heads of state bodies and organizations is to eliminate the causes and conditions that contribute to corruption in the relevant area. offences, through the implementation of effective internal anti-corruption measures, the introduction of mechanisms for accountability and openness of their activities, practical measures to ensure compliance with ethical rules and prevent conflicts of interest. According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Combating Corruption”, the system of measures to prevent corruption includes:

1. Measures to prevent corruption in public administration.
2. Measures to prevent corruption in the field of socio-economic development and entrepreneurship.
3. Measures to prevent and resolve conflicts of interest.
4. Measures to prevent corruption in the field of administrative procedures.
5. Measures to prevent corruption in the field of public procurement.
6. Anti-corruption expertise of legal acts and their projects.

Internal anti-corruption measures

¹ Н.Н. Вопленко. Правовые отношения: понятия и классификация//Исторические и общетеоретические проблемы. Вестник ВолГУ. Серия 5. Вып. 6. 2003—2004 – С.88.

In international practice, there are different approaches to the definition of a system for the prevention of corruption. For example, the anti-corruption system in the Netherlands includes, inter alia, the following key procedural and institutional measures:

- a system for monitoring the possible risks of corruption in state and public organizations and strict control over the activities of persons at risk;
- a system of punishments for corruption, with the main measure being the prohibition to work in state organizations and the loss of all social benefits provided by the public service;
- a system of rewarding positive actions of officials, aimed at ensuring that it is beneficial for an official both materially and morally to behave honestly and efficiently;
- A state security system to combat corruption has been created, such as a special police force with significant powers to detect cases of corruption. Similar measures are also applied in Israel and Canada.

Other countries also practice successful anti-corruption measures. In particular, civil society, as an institution inherent in a democratic regime, can increase the effectiveness of the activities of independent anti-corruption commissions. Successfully similar bodies function in Hong Kong, Singapore, Malaysia, Taiwan².

Analyze of the internal anti-corruption measures

In this regard, today the issue of developing effective internal anti-corruption programs is acute, since, according to public opinion polls conducted by the

² Гилевская М.А. Передовые национальные антикоррупционные стратегии [www.corupti.net/rus/2/html].

Izhtimoiy Fikr Center from 2016 to 2018, the level of corruption and bribery in some areas has increased several times. For example, according to citizens in the field of healthcare and medicine, corruption has doubled over 3 years (in 2016 - 26.1%, in 2017 - 37.6%, in 2018 - 43.7%). In the field of education, 34.3% of citizens who considered corruption in 2016 changed their minds to 39.4% in 2018, and in the tax sector there was an increase from 7% to 12.2%.

According to the results of the public opinion poll "Fighting Corruption in the Mirror of Public Opinion", conducted by the above-mentioned center, healthcare, the system of higher and public education are identified as areas subject to corruption, followed by courts, prosecutor's offices, internal affairs bodies, tax authorities and authorities. sanitary and epidemiological supervision and control (OECD, 2019).

For example, In 2021, 3,769 criminal cases of corruption against 5,483 people across the country were sent to the courts for consideration. Compared to 2020, the number of criminal cases sent to court increased by 2,621, and the number of persons prosecuted increased by 3,760, or 218 percent.

In 2020, as a result of corruption-related crimes, the state and society suffered material damage in the amount of 500 billion 102 million soums, of which 355 billion soums or 71 percent reimbursed. And in 2021, the amount of material damage amounted to 1 trillion 282 billion soums, of which 887 billion soums or 69.1 percent reimbursed.

For internal management of corruption risks, in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 6, 2021 No. 5177, state bodies and entities with a state share in the authorized capital, including banks, are obliged to implement and effectively operate the internal anti-corruption control system.

To date, the Internal Anti-Corruption Control Units operate in 88 government agencies, the work of 52 of which is not fully established.

At the same time, the Anti-Corruption Agency studied and analyzed the observance by local authorities of their obligations to post socially significant information on the official website and other information resources.

Conclusions

Based on the foregoing, we can conclude that the internal measures taken to combat corruption are not effective, and sometimes exacerbate the position of state bodies in front of the public. In this regard, the assessment of corruption risks arising from the implementation of the assigned tasks and functions, which must be formed on the basis of internal and external sources, is of particular importance:

regulatory legal acts and internal acts of state bodies regulating the implementation of functions for which corruption risks are assessed (for example, regulations on structural divisions, job descriptions of employees, etc.);

materials of internal audits, including internal audits;

the results of the meetings of the Ethics Commission;

reports on the facts of inducing an employee to commit corruption offenses;

results of a survey of stakeholders, recipients of public services, experts, representatives of civil society institutions and other interested parties, including sociological research;

statistical data on offenses in the field of activity of the state body;

appeals of citizens and legal entities to communication channels intended for reporting information about corrupt practices;

appeals of civil society institutions and information in the media containing information about corruption offenses or facts of non-compliance by employees of state bodies with the rules of ethical behavior;

comments on social networks;

results of anti-corruption monitoring of internal anti-corruption programs;

materials submitted by law enforcement agencies, including acts of prosecutorial response, materials on criminal cases and others.

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